

Synthesis and spectroscopic identification of cobalt(III) complexes with 5-methyl-3-formylpyrazole-*N*(4)-dipropylthiosemicarbazone (HMPzNPr₂) : X-ray crystal structure of [Co(MPzNPr₂)₂]NO₃·H₂O

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The coordination mode of the title ligand, HMPzNPr₂ (synthesized for the first time and characterized by elemental analysis, mass, IR and ¹H NMR spectral parameters), is reported by solid state isolation and physicochemical identification of cobalt(III) complexes, [Co(MPzNPr₂)₂]X·H₂O (X = Cl, Br, ClO₄, BF₄ and NO₃). Electronic spectral features of the diamagnetic Co^{III} species classify them as six-coordinate distorted octahedral ones. IR spectra (4000–200 cm⁻¹) of the uncomplexed HMPzNPr₂ and its complexes have indicated a monodeprotonated tridentate NNS function of the primary ligand molecule through the pyrazolyl (tertiary) ring nitrogen, azomethine nitrogen and thiolato sulfur atom. ¹H NMR data (in *d*₆ DMSO at 300 MHz) for the free ligand and those of its Co^{III} complexes are commensurate with the NNS tridenticity of the monodeprotonated HMPzNPr₂, as ascertained from down-field shift of the relevant protons adjacent to the bonding sites. X-Ray crystallography of [Co(MPzNPr₂)₂]NO₃·H₂O (*P* $\bar{1}$, triclinic) has authenticated a CoN₄S₂ octahedral coordination with severe distortion as evidenced from selected bond parameters; the average Co–N (azomethine), Co–N (pyrazolyl) and Co–S (thiolato) bond lengths are found to be 1.894(4), 1.956(4) and 2.214(2) Å, respectively. The anion (NO₃⁻) is H-bonded with the imino-proton of the pyrazolyl ring of one primary ligand molecule and at the same time the associated water molecule is also H-bonded with the nitrate ion.

Heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones (TSCs) have attracted much interest in chemistry and biology due to their antibacterial, antimalarial, antitumour and antiviral activities, and they represent an important series of compounds because of potentially beneficial biological activities¹. In several instances, the highest *in vivo* activity is associated with a metal ion complex rather than the parent TSC². Pyrazole derivatives with potential binding sites (with a metal ion) have long been the focal point of attention^{3–5}, because of their well acclaimed medicinal values⁶. In an attempt towards establishing a correlation between the structural nature of transition metal ion complexes of heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones and their potential biological activities, we report herein, the synthesis and spectroscopic characterization of a series of Co^{III} complexes with 5-methyl-3-formylpyrazole-*N*(4)-dipropylthiosemicarbazone (HMPzNPr₂) (Fig. 1) together with X-ray crystal structure of [Co(MPzNPr₂)₂]NO₃·H₂O as a part of our comprehensive effort and in continuation of our earlier publications⁷.

Results and Discussion

All these cobalt(III) complexes give satisfactory C, H, N

Fig. 1. HMPzNPr₂.

and Co analyses and conform to the general composition, [Co(MPzNPr₂)₂]X·H₂O (X = Cl, Br, ClO₄, BF₄ and NO₃). The molar conductance values in methanol (303 K) classify them as 1 : 1 electrolytes⁸ (Table 1) and the complexes are diamagnetic (at 300 K) as expected for a low spin *d*⁶ ion.

Spectroscopy :

It is documented that 6-coordinate cobalt(III) complexes should give rise to two spin-allowed and two spin-forbidden ligand field bands from the ¹A_{1g} ground state⁹; these are ¹A_{1g} → ³T_{1g}, ¹A_{1g} → ³T_{2g}, ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{1g} and ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{2g} transitions, respectively¹⁰. The diffuse reflectance spectra of all the reported cobalt(III) complexes are very much similar in nature and are characterized by three bands in the regions 15105–15455 (¹A_{1g} → ³T_{2g}), 21050–21835 (¹A_{1g}

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Table 1. Analytical and conductivity data of the complexes*

Compd.	Analysis % Found/(Calcd.)				Conductivity Ω^{-1} $\text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$
	C	H	N	M	
[Co(MPzNPr ₂) ₂]Cl·H ₂ O	44.7 (44.7)	6.5 (6.5)	21.7 (21.7)	9.1 (9.1)	89
[Co(MPzNPr ₂) ₂]Br·H ₂ O	41.8 (41.8)	6.1 (6.1)	20.4 (20.3)	8.5 (8.6)	84
[Co(MPzNPr ₂) ₂]ClO ₄ ·H ₂ O	40.7 (40.7)	5.9 (5.9)	19.8 (19.8)	8.3 (8.3)	110
[Co(MPzNPr ₂) ₂]BF ₄ ·H ₂ O	41.5 (41.4)	6.0 (6.0)	20.3 (20.1)	8.4 (8.5)	107
[Co(MPzNPr ₂) ₂]NO ₃ ·H ₂ O	42.9 (42.9)	6.2 (6.2)	22.9 (22.9)	8.7 (8.8)	95

*All complexes are coloured reddish brown.

→ ¹T_{1g}) and 23925–24750 cm⁻¹ (¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{2g}) which correspond to an overall octahedral symmetry. As the observed lower energy bands are not split to a greater extent, the reported Co^{III} complexes are indicated not to be *trans*-isomers⁹. The electronic spectra of the methanolic solutions of the complexes exhibit two bands in the region 43105–44050 (log ε = 4.675–4.699) and 30485–30865 cm⁻¹ (log ε = 4.62–4.64 dm³ cm⁻¹ mol⁻¹), attributable to intraligand charge transfer bands (π → π* and n → π*, respectively). The spectra also show a shoulder at 25510–26315 cm⁻¹ (log ε = 3.986–4.095 dm³ cm⁻¹ mol⁻¹) which may arise due to S → Co^{III} charge transfer (LMCT) bands. The absence of any d → d transition bands may be due to the masking of d → d bands by strong CT bands.

The characteristic IR bands (4000–200 cm⁻¹) for the free ligand (HMPzNPr₂) when compared with those of its Co^{III} complexes provide meaningful information regarding the bonding sites of the primary ligand molecule (Table 2). A negative shift in ν_{CH=N} band (~1611 cm⁻¹) in the spectrum of the free ligand to lower value (1592–1597 cm⁻¹) in its complexes is consistent with coordination of the azomethine nitrogen to the central cobalt(III) ion, the IR bands at 465–480 cm⁻¹ in the complexes are then assignable to ν_{Co-N}¹¹. An intense band around 867 cm⁻¹ in the free ligand spectrum is due to ν_{C=S} which has been found to

Table 2. IR spectral data (cm⁻¹) for the ligand and its Co^{III} complexes

Compd.	ν _{CH=N}	ν _{C=N}	ν _{C=S}	ν _{Co-N}	ν _{Co-N}	ν _{Co-S}
	(azome- thine)	(pyra- zole)		(azome- thine)	(pyra- zole)	
HMPzNPr ₂	1611	1505	867	-	-	-
[Co(MPzNPr ₂) ₂]Cl·H ₂ O	1595	1520	790	465	270	350
[Co(MPzNPr ₂) ₂]Br·H ₂ O	1597	1515	795	472	285	362
[Co(MPzNPr ₂) ₂]ClO ₄ ·H ₂ O	1594	1530	780	475	273	375
[Co(MPzNPr ₂) ₂]BF ₄ ·H ₂ O	1595	1532	775	468	280	380
[Co(MPzNPr ₂) ₂]NO ₃ ·H ₂ O	1592	1525	792	480	275	378

shift to lower frequency regions (775–795 cm⁻¹) in the complexes pointing to the coordination of the thiol sulfur to cobalt(III); moreover, a new band at the region 350–380 cm⁻¹ in the complexes is assignable to ν_{Co=S}^{7c}. The free ligand bands at 1505 and 610 cm⁻¹ assignable to ν_{C=N} (ring) and the in-plane deformation of the pyrazole ring are shifted to higher wavenumbers, recommending the tertiary ring nitrogen atom (²N) as a possible bonding site^{7a,12,13}.

The ¹H NMR spectra of the complexes (Table 3) when compared with that of the free ligand (HMPzNPr₂) point out the following. (i) The peak due to imino ²NH (at the thiosemicarbazone part) at δ 10.71 in the free ligand disappears after complexation. This indicates that presence of cobalt(III) ion undergoes deprotonation followed by coordination to the metal ion through thiolato sulfur atom. (ii) Terminal -N(*n*-Pr)₂ peaks showing slightly downfield shifts are ascribed to coordination of the thiol sulfur to Co^{III} resulting in reduced electron density at terminal N-atom of -N(*n*-Pr)₂. (iii) Maximum downfield shift occurs with azomethine -CH proton appearing at δ 8.38–8.41 in the complex molecules corresponding to δ 8.09 in the free ligand as expected due to coordination of the azomethine nitrogen to the central Co^{III} ion. (iv) The shifting of ⁴CH (the pyrazole ring) from δ 6.20 (free ligand) to 6.45–6.50 in the complexes are reasonable with the proposition that pyrazole ring ²N (tertiary) coordinates the cobalt(III) ion. ¹H NMR spectra, thus, provide support for the bonding characteristics of the primary ligand (HMPzNPr₂) in forming complexes with

Table 3. ¹H NMR spectral data (δ ppm) for the ligand and its Co^{III} complexes relative to TMS

Compd.	NH (imino)	azomethine -C-H	ring (Pz) C ₅ -CH ₃	ring (Pz) C ₄ -H	-N-(CH ₂ -C-C) ₂	-N-(C-CH ₂ -C) ₂	-N(C-C-CH ₃) ₂
HMPzNPr ₂	10.71	8.09	2.48	6.20	3.40	1.63	0.86
[Co(MPzNPr ₂) ₂]Cl·H ₂ O	-	8.41	2.50	6.45	3.52	2.11	1.05
[Co(MPzNPr ₂) ₂]Br·H ₂ O	-	8.38	2.61	6.48	3.55	2.15	0.99
[Co(MPzNPr ₂) ₂]ClO ₄ ·H ₂ O	-	8.40	2.57	6.50	3.50	1.99	1.07
[Co(MPzNPr ₂) ₂]BF ₄ ·H ₂ O	-	8.38	2.50	6.48	3.53	2.01	1.01
[Co(MPzNPr ₂) ₂]NO ₃ ·H ₂ O	-	8.40	2.51	6.45	3.49	2.10	1.04

cobalt(III) through pyrazolyl ring nitrogen ²N (tertiary), azomethine nitrogen and the thiolato sulfur atom ^{7c}.

Crystal structure of [Co(MPzNPr₂)₂]NO₃·H₂O :

A molecular view of the complex together with the atom numbering scheme is shown in Fig. 2. The structure con-

Fig. 2. ORTEP plot of [Co(MPzNPr₂)₂]NO₃·H₂O showing the atom numbering scheme

tains [Co(MPzNPr₂)₂]⁺ cation and NO₃⁻ anion and a water of crystallization. The Co^{III} atom is octahedrally coordinated

Table 4. Crystal data

Empirical formula	C ₂₄ H ₄₂ CoN ₁₁ O ₄ S ₂	
Formula weight	671.74	
Temperature	293(2) K	
Wavelength	0.71073 Å	
Crystal system	Triclinic	
Space group	P $\bar{1}$	
Unit cell dimensions	$a = 8.487(3)$ Å	$\alpha = 94.73(2)^\circ$
	$b = 13.522(4)$ Å	$\beta = 95.63(2)^\circ$
	$c = 14.772(3)$ Å	$\gamma = 96.95(3)^\circ$
Volume, Z	1668.9(8) Å ³ , 2	
Density (calculated)	1.337 mg m ⁻³	
Absorption coefficient	0.686 mm ⁻¹	
$F(000)$	708	
Reflections collected	6290	
Independent reflections	5859 ($R_{int} = 0.0427$)	
Completeness to $\theta = 25.00^\circ$	99.9%	
Goodness-of-fit on F^2 (S)	1.000	
Final R indices [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	$R1 = 0.0824$, $wR2 = 0.1590$	
R indices (all data)	$R1 = 0.1794$, $wR2 = 0.2000$	
Largest diff peak and hole	0.472 and -0.332 eÅ ⁻³	

by two similar tridentate ligands through pyrazolyl nitrogen atoms [N(1A) and N(1B)], the azomethine nitrogen atoms [N(3A) and N(3B)] and thiolato sulfur atoms [S(1A) and S(1B)]. The relevant bond distances and angles with their e.s.d's in parenthesis are summarized in Table 5 which are in well agreement with the literature values¹⁷⁻¹⁹. The Co-

Table 5. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles (°) with e.s.d's in parentheses

Co-S(1A)	2.207(2)	Co-S(1B)	2.222(2)
Co-N(1A)	1.956(4)	Co-N(1B)	1.955(4)
Co-N(3A)	1.896(4)	Co-N(3B)	1.891(4)
N(3B)-Co-N(3A)	179.2(2)	N(3B)-Co-N(1A)	98.84(19)
N(3A)-Co-N(1A)	81.71(19)	N(3B)-Co-N(1B)	81.75(18)
N(3A)-Co-N(1B)	97.61(18)	N(1A)-Co-N(1B)	89.99(18)
N(3B)-Co-S(1A)	94.05(14)	N(3A)-Co-S(1A)	85.39(15)
N(1A)-Co-S(1A)	167.08(14)	N(1B)-Co-S(1A)	90.94(14)
N(3B)-Co-S(1B)	85.12(14)	N(3A)-Co-S(1B)	95.53(14)
N(1A)-Co-S(1B)	90.31(13)	N(1B)-Co-S(1B)	166.75(14)
S(1A)-Co-S(1B)	91.73(7)		
NO ₃ bonding			
N-O(1)	1.254(7)	N-O(2)	1.208(7)
		N-O(3)	1.248(7)
NO ₃ angles			
O(1)-N-O(2)	119.6(6)	O(2)-N-O(3)	120.8(6)
		O(1)-N-O(3)	119.5(6)

N(1A, 1B) (pyrazolyl), Co-N(3A, 3B) (hydrazinic) and Co-S(1A, 1B) (thiolato) distances are [1.956(4), 1.955(4)], [1.896(4), 1.891(4)], [2.207(2), 2.222(2)], respectively, in two ligands.

Analysis of angular distribution show that the coordination octahedron is highly distorted. N(1)-Co-S(1) angles are 167.08° and 166.75° for two ligands, respectively. The maximum distortion from ideal octahedral geometry occurs for N(1A)-Co-S(3A) (81.71°) and N(1B)-Co-S(3B) (81.75°). Steric interactions account for this distortion from ideal octahedral geometry.

Coordination of the metal atom with two tridentate ligands results in the formation of four five-membered chelate rings [Co-N(1A)-C(4A)-C(5A)-N(3A)], [Co-N(3A)-N(4A)-C(6A)-S(1A)], [Co-N(3B)-N(4B)-C(6B)-S(1B)], [Co-N(1B)-C(4B)-C(5B)-N(3B)]. From the analysis of the dihedral angles about the bonds of these chelate rings, it appears that they are planar in nature and they form extended coplanar ring system with pyrazolyl ring. This extended coplanar system approaches each other orthogonally.

N(3) nitrogens of both ligands A and B are in ideal *trans*-position. The pyrazolyl nitrogen and hydrazinic nitrogens are in *cis*-position and the hydrazinic nitrogen and thiolato sulfur are in *cis*-position also. This conformation is necessary for its participation as a tridentate NNS ligand. Also

the orthogonality of two ligands is very much necessary to form the coordination octahedron. Nitrate geometry is almost ideal as evidenced from the bond distances and angles (Table 5).

Table 6. Details of hydrogen bonding distance (Å) and angles (°)

D = proton donor, A = proton acceptor

D-H...A	D-H	D...A	H...A	D-H...A
N(2A)-H(2A)...O(1)	0.927(6)	2.766(7)	1.842(7)	170.2(6)
O(1W)-H(1W1)...O(3)	0.811(6)	2.764(7)	1.947(7)	169.1(6)

The hydrogen bonding scenario is as follows : O(1) of NO₃ anion is hydrogen bonded to N(2A) of the pyrazolyl ring of ligand A. Another oxygen O(3) of NO₃ is hydrogen bonded to water oxygen. Thus two oxygens of anion nitrate are holding the coordinated ligand system and the water of crystallisation. The geometrical parameters are given in Table 6. The packing diagram is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Packing diagram of [Co(MPzNPr₂)₂]NO₃·H₂O.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade and used without further purification. The title ligand, HMPzNPr₂ was synthesized for the first time in our laboratory by a similar but appropriately modified method¹⁴ followed by the final transamination¹⁵ of S-methyldithiocarbamate of 5-methyl-3-formylpyrazole (HMPzSMe) with dipropylamine : white crystallised product (~60%, from ethanol), m.p. 158–159° (Found : C, 54.0; H, 7.8; N, 26.6. C₁₂H₂₁N₅S calcd. for : C, 53.9; H, 7.8; N, 26.4%); ¹H NMR δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 2.48 (3H, s), 6.20 (1H, s), 8.09 (1H, s), 10.71 (1H, b), 3.40 (4H, t), 1.63 (4H, m), 0.86 (6H, t); *m/z* 267 (M⁺, 58%).

The reported Co^{III} complexes were prepared by refluxing ethanolic solution of the ligand (0.00105 mol) and the corresponding hydrated Co^{II} salts (0.000525 mol) in a water-bath for 1 h. The desired Co^{III} complexes, in each case, were obtained by slow evaporation of the dark brown solution. The reddish brown crystalline solid was filtered off;

washed with cold ethanol and dried over anhydrous CaCl₂ (yield 75–80%).

Elemental analyses (C, H and N) were done at I.A.C.S., Kolkata, with a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O analyzer. The cobalt content of the complexes were determined gravimetrically as anhydrous CoSO₄. Molar conductance of the complexes in methanolic solution were measured with a Systronics 304 conductivity meter. The electronic spectra of the complexes in methanolic solution and the diffuse reflectance spectra were recorded on a Hitachi U-3501 spectrophotometer. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Jasco FT/IR-420 spectrophotometer at Burdwan University. Magnetic measurements were made in the polycrystalline state on a PAR 155 sample vibrating magnetometer at I.A.C.S., Kolkata. ¹H NMR spectra (DMSO-*d*₆) were recorded with a Bruker AM300L (300 MHz) superconducting FT NMR.

Mass spectrum of the ligand was done at C.D.R.I., Lucknow, with a Jeol JMS-D 300 spectrometer.

X-Ray structure determination : The compound crystallized in the triclinic space group *P* $\bar{1}$. X-Ray data collected from a crystal of dimension (0.04 × 0.42 × 0.29 mm) from a Nonius MACH3 diffractometer, using graphite monochromatized Mo-K α radiation [λ (Mo-K α) = 0.7103].

The accurate cell parameters were determined by least-squares refinement of the setting angles of 25 reflections. Intensity data were collected using the same radiation using ω - 2θ scan technique in the range $2 \leq \theta \leq 25^\circ$ with $0 \leq h \leq 10$, $-16 \leq k \leq 15$, $-17 \leq l \leq 17$. During the process of data collection three standard reflections were checked periodically to ensure the stability of the crystal. A total of 6290 reflections were collected of which 5859 reflections were independent with the completeness of the data of 99.9%. Absorption correction was applied using SHELXA having absorption coefficient of 0.686 cm⁻¹.

The structure of the complex was solved using SHELX86 programme package¹⁶. The position of the Co ion was determined from a three-dimensional Patterson synthesis and from the known phases of the Co ion, positions of the rest of the non-hydrogen atoms were located by successive Fourier synthesis.

Non-hydrogen atomic positions were initially refined with full-matrix least-squares refinement using SHELXTL program. The end atoms in the propyl group in both the ligands are highly disordered as reflected in their high temperature factor and they are assumed to occupy two or three multiple positions with different occupancy. All other atoms except these were refined anisotropically. Hydrogens were generated at this stage and further least-squares refinements were carried out. The model of the structure refined upto residual factor $R1 = 0.08$ [with $I > 2\sigma(I)$], $wR2 = 0.1590$ and with all data the values are $R1 = 0.1794$, $wR2 = 0.2000$. We anticipate that the highly disordered state of the two propyl group mainly contribute to the high residual factor. The crystal data is given in Table 4.

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